

TENSILE BEHAVIOUR OF THIN-PLY COMPOSITES

Haihong Wu¹, Zheng Zhang¹, Shichao Li¹, Liyong Tong^{2*} and Jiawei Lu²

¹ College of Mechanical Engineering, Henan University of Technology, Zhenzhou, China

² School of Aerospace, Mechanical & Mechatronic Eng., The University of Sydney, Australia
liyong.tong@sydney.edu.au

Keywords: Tensile properties, Thin-ply, Carbon fibre, Composite plates, Test

ABSTRACT

This paper presents preliminary experimental results on the effects of ply thickness on mechanical behaviour of carbon fibre reinforced composites prepared with thin plies and normal plies. Carbon fibre reinforced composite laminate plates were fabricated using plies of two different thicknesses, i.e. 0.03 mm and 0.1 mm, respectively. Cross-sectional microstructures and tensile behaviours of unidirectional laminates fabricated with the thin ply and the normal ply were investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites (CFRP) fabricated using standard ply thickness of 0.1 mm to 0.25 mm are widely used in aerospace, automobile and energy sector due to its high specific stiffness and strength. In recent years, thin-ply laminates receive a growing attention due to some benefits offered by thin plies over standard thick plies in the context of first-ply-failure, delamination, ultimate strength and fatigue life [1-3]. Thin ply laminates refer to the laminates that are fabricated by using plies with thickness less than 0.1 mm. One of the processing methods used to fabricate thin ply is to use pneumatic flow to spread carbon fibre tow to desired width [1]. The pioneering experimental work of Sihm et al. [1] showed that thin-ply laminates can delay or even suppress matrix microcracking and delamination damage for static, fatigue and impact loadings. More recently, Amacher et al. [2] and Cugnoni et al [3] obtained similar observations via conducting a broad range of experiments including coupons and bolted joints made of thin plies with a thickness of approximately 0.04 mm. Frossard et al [4] and Bullegas et al [5] investigated the intralaminar and translaminar fracture behavior of thin-ply composites. Despite these progresses in understanding thin-ply composites, there still lacks fundamental understanding of the potential benefits and issues thin-ply composites can offer.

In this study, an in-house equipment for producing thin ply prepregs for fabrication of thin-ply composites is developed and presented. Laminate samples made from 0.03 mm thin plies and 0.1 mm normal plies were prepared. Cross sectional microstructures of these two groups of samples are examined with distinct features identified. Tensile failure strength and strains as well as failure mechanisms were determined.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The carbon fiber (CF) tow used was 12K T700SC from Toray. It comprises 12,000 bundled CF filaments packed at a high density with each filament having a nominal diameter of 7 μm , a specific density of 1.8 g/cm^3 , a tensile strength of 4.9 GPa, a tensile modulus of 230 GPa and an elongation of 2.1%. The resin used was EP resin 3513 obtained from Zhonghang Composite Technology Company.

2.1 Sample Preparation

To understand the effects of tow spreading extent on the performance of its composites, the chosen CF tow was spread into 20 and 40 mm in width with uniform fiber filament distribution by using an in-house multi-stage pneumatic spreading technology. The spread CF tows were subsequently impregnated in the EP resin 3513 under 70°C, and then were rolled by two heating rollers to obtain the unidirectional CFRP prepreg tape of uniform thickness. Two types of unidirectional CFRP prepreg

tapes of 0.1 and 0.03 mm thick with a CF weight fraction of 60% and 52% respectively were fabricated. The fabricating process is illustrated as in Fig. 1.

A CF tow, as shown in Fig. 1(a), was put on the unwinding table which could be moved in 3-D space according to the instructions from the camera to prevent the fiber from deviating from the center line of the spread width, as shown in Fig. 2(b). The fiber was spread by means of multi-stage air flow chamber, and the flow was adjusted through an air-flow meter based on the spread width image collected by another camera as shown in Fig.2(c). The fiber spread into the desired width as in Fig. 2(d) was directly guided onto the release paper to be infiltrated with epoxy, as shown in Fig. 2(e). Finally, the prepreg tape was rolled up in a I-wheel as shown in Fig. 2(f).

The CFRP prepreg tapes were then stacked and cured by using a vacuum compression molding to produce a unidirectional (UD) laminate plate of $250 \times 250 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$. The curing temperature was set to be 130°C , the curing time was two hours and the curing pressure was 0.5 MPa. In order to reduce the porosity in the samples, gas removal channels and pre-compacting technique were employed during the process of lay-up to produce laminate. After curing, fiber weight fraction W_f was measured using the resin burn-off method. From the CFRP plates, specimens of 250 mm long and 15 mm wide were prepared by using water cutting machine for mechanical performance testing of the laminate samples.

Figure 1: Schematics of the fabrication process of prepreg tape

2.2 Testing Method and Procedures

The cross sectional images of the microstructure of the CFRP specimens were obtained by using an optical microscope. The contents of the resin-rich pockets greater than a chosen threshold was identified and then estimated by using a statistical method based on the measured results with transparent graft paper. The statistical sample size used was 15 by $15 \mu\text{m}$.

The tensile tests were conducted for both groups of specimens using an CRIMP universal testing machine. The load was applied by displacement control with a loading rate of 0.5 mm/min . Fig. 2

depicts the image of the tensile test set-up with a digital image correlation system and an acoustic emission system for measuring strain fields and micro cracking occurrence respectively.

Figure 2: Image of the tensile test set-up

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure

Fig. 3 depicts the cross-sectional images of the unidirectional CFRP specimens prepared using plies of 0.03 mm and 0.1 mm respectively. It is noted that the image in Fig. 3(b) appears to more distinct and thicker resin rich layers separating adjacent plies than that in Fig. 3(a); and the relatively large resin rich pockets tend to occur between two adjacent plies in Fig. 3(b).

In addition to the distribution of the resin-rich pockets, the state of the fiber arranged in the UDL was investigated, as shown in Fig. 4(a) and 4(b), and the surface morphology of the ply was observed with AFM, as shown in Fig. 4(c) and 4(d).

(a) 0.03 mm

(b) 0.1 mm

Figure 3: Cross section views of the specimens prepared with (a) 0.03 mm plies and (b) 0.1 mm plies.

(a) 0.03 mm ply

(b) 0.1 mm ply

Figure 4: Fiber alignment in the ply and the surface morphology

The results of the Fig. 4 suggest that the distribution of the CFs in the ultra-thin ply sample is more uniform than that of the thick-ply sample. The difference of the uniformity can be attributed to the manufacturing process of the two laminates with different ply thickness. The 0.03 mm thin and 0.1 mm thick ply prepreg generally arrange approximately 3~4 layers and 9-13 layers CFs in the thickness direction, respectively. For the thick prepreg, the inhomogeneity between different layers of the multilayer CFs is easy to occur, resulting in the possibility of the deflection and even damage of the CFs increases, which further leads to a substantial decrease of the tensile performance.

In addition, the surface morphology is different in these two kinds plies, as shown in Fig.4(c) and 4(d). The scale of the ridges is small in the thin-ply sample, which increases the interface bonding energy based on the theory of interface. It is known that the interface bonding energy presents an important effect on the mechanical properties of CFRP.

3.2 Tensile Behavior

The measured stress increases almost linearly with the recorded strain from a strain gauge bonded at the center of all 0.1 and 0.03 mm specimens as shown in Fig. 5. Table 1 and 2 tabulates the measured strength, ultimate strain, Young's modulus and their average values and standard deviations for the 0.03mm and 0.1 specimens. It is evident that the standard deviations in all these three quantities for the 0.03mm specimens are larger than those for the 0.1mm specimens. This indicates that the quality, preparation and testing of the specimens, in particular the 0.03mm ones, could be improved. It is also worth noting that the carbon fiber weight fraction for the 0.03 mm specimen is 55%, which 9% lower than that of the 0.1 mm specimen. This could be a contributing factor to the results of similar tensile strength between the 0.03 and 0.1 mm specimens.

Fig. 6 depicts the acoustic emission diagrams for the two specimens prepared using 0.1 mm and 0.03 mm plies. It is evident that the acoustic intensity of the 0.03 and 0.1 mm specimens attains its first peak ($>1V$) at $\sim 166s$ and $\sim 233s$, indicating that the first damage recorded happened in 0.03 mm specimen earlier. There are more peaks ($>1V$) occurred in the 0.1 mm specimen than in the 0.03 mm one.

Figure 5. Measured stress-strain curves in tensile tests

Sample Number	Strength (GPa)	Strain (%)	Young's modulus (GPa)
1*	2.26	1.33	170.6
2	2.27	1.68	133.7
3	2.12	1.70	133.5
Average	2.22	1.57	145.9
(stdv)	(±0.08)	(±0.21)	(±21.4)

* Sample 1 did not fail due to reaching load limit of Instron 5567; Sample 2 was a repeat of sample 1 using MTS 810

Table 1: Tensile test for the 0.03 mm thin-ply samples ($V_f=0.45$)

Sample Number	Strength (GPa)	Strain (%)	Young's modulus (GPa)
1	2.22	1.63	136.0
2	2.17	1.61	134.7
3	2.29	1.65	139.3
Average	2.23	1.63	136.6
(stdv)	(±0.06)	(±0.022)	(±2.37)

Table 2: Tensile test for the 0.1 mm thick-ply samples ($V_f=0.54$)

Fig.7a~7b show the fracture and rupture behaviors of the ultra-thin and conventional ply laminated sample during the tensile test, respectively. It is found that there is almost no interlaminar damage (interior delamination) in the thickness direction of the ultra-thin ply laminates, which fracture and fatigue behavior are mainly shown to be matrix (epoxy resin) cracking. However, compared with the high bundling of the ultra-thin ply laminates under tensile loading, the conventional ply laminate shows more branching, interior delaminating as well as matrix cracking during the test. The observed difference of the fracture behavior and tensile properties can be mutually confirmed, and they are both assumed to be correspondence to the distribution of CFs and the matrices. Additional study is needed to develop further understanding.

For ultra-thin ply laminates, because of the fiber and resin are uniform distributed, and the stress distribution is also uniform under tensile loading, which improves the load-carrying capacity of the laminated composites. Furthermore, during the deformation process of the tested samples, the propagation of cracks can be hindered, shifted or even stopped by the surrounding fibers easily once the damage occurs. Therefore, short and fine cracks are observed in the fracture morphology, as shown

in Fig.8(a). It can be also observed from Fig.8(a) that a layer of resin is evenly adhered to every fiber after being pulled out in the fracture surface, and there are almost no holes left by the fibers after being pulled out from the resin matrix, indicating a well-bonded interface between the fibers and the resin matrix.

(a) Specimen with 0.03 mm thin plies

(b) Specimen with 0.1 mm thick plies

Figure 6: Acoustic emission diagrams for specimens with (a) thin plies and (b) thick plies.

(a)The fracture process and the morphology of the thin-ply

(b) The fracture process and the morphology of thick-ply samples

Figure 7: The macro fracture morphologies of the samples

In contrast, the inhomogeneous resin-rich zones of the conventional ply sample significantly reduce the load-carrying capacity of the laminates. Because of the weakness of resin properties, once cracks are formed, stress concentration will occur in the resin-rich zone of large size, leading to rapid crack propagation. It can be verified by the large penetrating cracks shown in Fig. 8(b) (circled).

In addition, it can be also observed from Fig. 8(b) that the number of holes left by the fiber pulled out from the resin matrix increases obviously due to the tensile load in the section after fracture of the sample, which are attributed to the poorly implanting CF bundles and large-size resin-rich zones.

Therefore, the tensile strength decreases at the same strain due to interfacial debonding between the CFs and the matrix crack. Therefore a conclusion could be drawn that the ultra-thin ply method can improve the tensile properties of the laminated CFRCs, resulting from the uniform distribution of CFs in the matrices.

Figure 8: the macro fracture morphologies of the samples: (a) 0.03 mm and (b) 0.1 mm

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the ultra-thin ply laminated carbon fiber composites with the ply thickness of 0.03 mm was successfully fabricated, and the difference of mechanical properties and tensile fracture behaviors between the ultra-thin ply and a conventional thin-ply composites with the ply thickness of 0.1mm were investigated. It is found that the conventional ply laminates not only have a lower tensile strength and strain-at-break, but also shows more branching, interior delaminating as well as matrix cracking during the tensile test, compared with the high bundling of the ultra-thin ply laminates under tensile loading. The further investigations of mechanism suggest that the different distribution of the resin-rich zones is the main reason on the tensile and fracture behavior of the laminates. The ultra-thinning of the laminated composites, which is benefited to the uniform distribution of CFs in the matrices, can hence improve the tensile properties and the fracture behaviors.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the support of the National Science Foundation of China via a grant (grant number: U1604253).

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Sihn, R.Y. Kim, K. Kawabe and S. Tsai, Experimental studies of thin-ply laminated composites, *Composite Science and Technology*, **67**, 2007, pp 996–1008.
- [2] R. Amacher, J. Cugnoni, J. Botsis, L. Sorensen, W. Smith and C. Dransfeld, Thin ply composites: experimental characterization and modeling of size-effects, *Composite Science and Technology*, **101**, 2014, pp 121-132.

- [3] J. Cugnoni, R. Amacher, S. Kohler, J. Brunner and J. Botsis, Towards aerospace grade thin-ply composites: effect of ply thickness, fibre, matrix and interlayer toughening on strength and damage tolerance, *Composites Science and Technology*, **168**, 2018, pp 467-477.
- [4] G. Frossard, J. Cugnoni, T. Gmür and J. Botsis, Ply thickness dependence of the intralaminar fracture in thin-ply carbon-epoxy laminates, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **109**, 2018, pp.95-104 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2018.03.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2018.03.001)).
- [5] G. Bullegas, S.T. Pinho and S. Pimenta, Engineering the translaminar fracture behaviour of thin-ply composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **131**(2), 2016, pp.110-122 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2016.06.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2016.06.002)).